

SCIENTIFIC-PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF THE ACTIVITY OF NECESSARY PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS

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ANNOTATION

In this article, the main terms encountered in the scientific pedagogical activity of the future physical education teacher, the correct organization of pedagogical activity, the future physical education teachers should pay special attention to during their scientific pedagogical activity. aspects and the need for an approach, as well as the organization of innovative and technological activities of the future physical education teacher are discussed.

Keywords: *Physical education, pedagogical activity, pedagogical skill, innovative activity of the future physical education teacher, creativity, technological approach.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the priorities of our country's policy is to raise a generation that is both physically and mentally healthy. Because today, in the conditions of globalization processes that are intensifying in the countries of the world, raising a highly moral and physically fit generation is one of the most important factors that determine the future of our country and realize the noble goals of our people. In the implementation of this good deed, its legal foundations have been created, and extensive work is being done.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In particular, the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev of June 3, 2017 "On measures for the development of physical education and mass sports" No. Decree No. PF-5368 "On measures to

fundamentally improve the management system" is of particular importance in the further development of this field. One of the main goals of these decrees and decisions is to further deepen theoretical and practical knowledge in this field, to correctly formulate the concepts and terms of skills and qualifications related to physical education. In fact, at a time when the processes of globalization are becoming more and more intense, the attention paid to physical education teachers, who are directly involved in the general and special physical training of young people, is gaining importance in this regard. After all, one of their important services is to direct students to educational, cultural, medical, industrial construction, and production professions, and secondly, they serve to a certain extent to arm them with special physical training. Today, the teachers who teach the young generation have fully mastered modern innovative technologies, have the skills to use information and communication tools wisely, and generally know all the secrets of education. is required. When studying the issues related to the scientific pedagogical activity of future physical education teachers, it is appropriate to analyze the content and essence of the concepts related to this phenomenon. In particular, we can see that the concept of "physical education" itself has several definitions.

"Physical education is a pedagogical process aimed at improving the human body morphologically and functionally, forming and improving basic movement skills, skills, and knowledge related to them, which are important for his life." Definitions such as "Physical education aimed at all-round training of the body, education aimed at strengthening health, physical exercises" are given. Whether he is a mathematician, physicist, historian, or physical education teacher in different areas, his work style is directly related to pedagogical activity. The meaningful and high-quality conduct of the lesson, in turn, is closely related to his pedagogical skill, pedagogical skills, pedagogical competence, and pedagogical activity in general. The famous Russian pedagogue V.A. Sukhomlinsky: "One of

the secrets of pedagogical leadership is to arouse interest in teachers' regular research and analysis of their work. "Whoever tries to distinguish between good and bad in his lessons, in his interactions with students, and to share his achievements and shortcomings in time, will have achieved half the success of pedagogical activity," he said. expressed. From this point of view, a young future physical education teacher who has just started his pedagogical career cannot relax physically and mentally or completely relax. As we know, this feeling is called "relaxation" in the science of psychology, and it is recognized as an assessment of negative situations in people's work.

In order for each future physical education teacher to fully acquire pedagogical skills: first, he must have mastered his subject based on the requirements of the time; secondly, to have psychological and pedagogical knowledge (to be able to use methods suitable for the character of students); thirdly, it is important that it contains pedagogical curiosity and self-sacrifice. Russian scientist I.P.Rachenko expresses the following opinion about pedagogical skills as a part of pedagogical art: "Pedagogical skills are the teacher's perfect mastery of pedagogical-psychological knowledge, professional qualifications and skills, interest in his profession, developed pedagogical thinking and intuition, it means moral-aesthetic attitude to life, confidence in one's own reasoning and strong will". Also, in the pedagogical activity of the future physical education teacher, it is most important for the future physical education teacher to be devoted to the teaching profession, to have a perfect knowledge of the teaching methodology of his subject, to be able to demonstrate his pedagogical skills, and to be able to apply pedagogical techniques in his place. is one of the important components.

It should be noted that every future physical education teacher is always engaged in his education and training in parallel with the delivery of physical exercises to students, and interacts with him. Since each student is constantly developing mentally, spiritually and physically, the future teacher should be in

constant communication with them, taking into account each of their psychological character and physiological characteristics, the mechanisms of influence. , first of all, it is necessary to study the theory of psychology and education in a perfect way, and constantly develop his professional activity. From this point of view, we believe that future physical education teachers should pay special attention to the following during their scientific and pedagogical activities:

- to have perfect mastery of the system of knowledge on physical education;
- having the skills and qualifications to fully deliver physical exercises to students;
- knowledge of the basis of general methodological sciences, in particular, current issues of state policy, along with mastering one's own science;
- able to independently analyze the social problems and processes taking place around them from their point of view;
- acquiring knowledge about the spiritual image of students during the educational process;
- the ability of students to apply modern pedagogical and psychological knowledge based on their age characteristics;
- able to independently acquire new knowledge, improve it and use it in their work on a scientific basis;
- being able to individually use regulatory legal documents in their scientific and pedagogical activities;
- compliance with the culture of the problem;
- able to analyze acquired knowledge based on a critical approach;
- able to convey acquired knowledge clearly to students;
- the formation of a sense of responsibility for one's profession;
- having mastered one of the foreign languages as a professional qualification or a means of exchange of scientific communication during the pedagogical activity;
- ability to effectively use modern information technologies;

- ability to use modern pedagogical technologies in pedagogical activity, etc.

CONCLUSION

Future teachers of physical education must have a perfect knowledge of the terms of physical culture used in their pedagogical activities. Of course, the use of terms by the teacher in a comprehensible, clear and appropriate way has a direct impact on the quality of the student's physical training. In fact, we all use the terms of physical culture today in our daily life.

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